

INVESTIGATING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SEASONALIZATION BASED ON STATISTICAL PARAMETERS IN NORMALIZING, MODELING AND FORECASTING INFLOW TIME SERIES

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ABSTRACT

To solve many problems such as estimation of average monthly river inflow, it is necessary to consider a time-dependent phenomenon which is involved in several factors. So, a stochastic model has to be obtained to calculate the probability of a future amount of inflow. Studying of river behavior and the ability to forecast the future events is a prerequisite for the preparation of optimization models. In the present study, methods for creating, diagnosis and assessing the rate of compatibility with seasonal ARIMA time series models have been provided. It is also supposed that the seasonal classification based on their statistical parameter similarities, could lead to a better normalized series in comparison to the other transformation methods. The discussed methods are suitable for continuous systems. The ARIMA method was used to predict the future amounts of the inflow into the Karaj reservoir by using its previous and present values. For implementing models, first, it is necessary to normalize the observed data with a logical transformation method considering seasonalization. The results showed that the best fitted model is an annual series ARIMA (1, 0, 1) (2, 1, 1)₁₂ with logarithmic transformation for forecasting models. It is also concluded that the 12 month forecast of inflow is better than 24 months in terms of the forecasted values.

KEYWORDS:

Time Series, Forecast, ARIMA, Karaj Reservoir, Seasonal Models

INTRODUCTION

It is obvious that forecasting the events play an important role in our daily life [1]. Time series are used as one of the most important methods to infer results for the future. Time-series models have been utilized to make reasonably accurate predictions in the areas of climate change such as rainfall, sunshine hours, temperatures as well as hydrologic process such as discharge forecasting ,etc. [2]. Accurate prediction of discharge is the key point to manage the surface water resources, especially to calculate the appropriate measures for flood and drought of water resources. Increasing water demand, shows the need to manage water resources in different areas, specifically in arid and semi-arid regions [3]. Therefore, achieving a reliable method to forecast the inflow of the river is crucial to plan for timely operation of water resources. Since the process related to water resources are often stochastic, they are used more than time series for analyzing and forecasting of these process. Time series is a set of observations which its attribute is time dependency. The main goal of those observations is to analyze past data of the series in order to generalize a pattern of estimation or to propose a model for the future. The results of data analysis of time series at the previous years have led to the usage of stochastic models which have been widely used recently. These models are developed in daily [4], monthly [5] and annual [6] formats. Such models could help that decision making relating to the operation of the system, will be carefully implemented and thus lead to optimal management [7, 8].

There are various methods to forecast time series. In general, they can be divided into two categories: traditional methods (or statistical methods) such as Simple Regression, Exponential Smoothing, Autoregressive (AR), Moving Average (MA), Autoregressive Moving Average (ARMA),

Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA), Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (SARIMA), and nontraditional methods such as Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS).

Since the beginning of 1960s, the widespread application of stochastic model structures has begun with the introduction and usage of models for annual and seasonal series. Similarly, Vogel and Stedinger [9] examined the values of stochastic models of river flows and applied them to design reservoirs. The results of study showed that the use of these models can improve the accuracy of dam's capacity estimation. Consequently, they managed to prove that the estimation of reservoir capacity of storage dams, which is based on fairly simple models with square average roots contains fewer errors than the final estimation, which is solely based on data statistics. Pereira et al. [10] used stochastic models of a river flow in the hydroelectricity system of Brazil and examined the amount of economic loss or benefit of applying various models in the system.

The basic trend of the classic moving average correlated models has been explained by Box and Jenkins [11]. Afterwards, these models faced some changes during the 1970s and 1980s so that they could create the models of seasonal time series. Spoila and Chander [12], Mcleod et al. [13, 14] have used seasonal autoregressive integrated moving average models in order to obtain the models of river flow. Mcleod and Hipel [15] used this model to analyze and solve the issues of watershed management. An extension of the congregational moving average correlated model had led to congregational fraction moving average correlated model that has been introduced by Granger and Joyeux [16] and Hosking [17].

Researchers often use ARIMA, SARIMA and also the deseasonalized model and the periodic autoregressive (PAR) in univariate time series [18]. Magar and Jothiparkash [19] used Multi-Linear Regression Method (MLR) to predict the daily flow of intermittent reservoirs. Then, they compared the results to the ARIMA models. Zhang et al. [20] presented a hybrid model consists of two methods Singular Spectrum Analysis (SSA) and ARIMA model for hydrological medium-term and long-term forecasts. Results show the best performance of the hybrid model.

It has been a long time that nontraditional methods, especially non-linear, are used because of having the characteristics like intelligence, flexibility and parallel processing to identify model and predicting the behavior of complex systems. Moreover, on some occasions, prediction and controlling of the parameters via traditional methods are very difficult or even impossible. So, researchers like Dong and Pedrycz [21], Yu [22, 23] used fuzzy logic; Guven [24] used linear genetic programming,

Muluye and Coulibaly [25] used Artificial Neural Networks to forecast their time series. Koutroumanidis et al. [26] used Genetic modeling for the optimal forecasting of hydrological time series.

Many other researchers also used a comparison of statistical and non-classical methods in order to estimate the accuracy of the proposed methods. But with all the advantages of non-traditional methods which were mentioned before, their application in practice has not developed properly because of different reasons, including imprecise of these methods and the complexity governing the selection and appropriate network architecture.

To check the forecast of time series of monthly inflow for oriented data models, Wu and Chau [27] compared 4 models: Auto-Regressive Moving Average (ARMA), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), K-Nearest-Neighbors (KNN) and Phase Space Reconstruction-based Artificial Neural Networks (PSR-ANN), which KNN model has the best performance among them. Abudu et al. [28] used hybrid modeling method; Transfer-Function Noise (TFN) and an Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) to predict monthly flow runoff during the Spring– Summer. The results show the better generalization ability and higher accuracy of hybrid modeling comparing to separated models.

Other studies have been done based on the use of a combination or comparison of traditional and non-traditional methods for forecasting time series such as ARIMA-ANN-GA [29], ARIMA-GA [30], ARIMA-FL-ANNs [31]. The main objective of this research is to investigate the potential of time series by seasonalization to model and forecast the inflow. This prepares the needed information for decision making in operation of the reservoirs.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Area. The catchment of Karaj is located between longitude east between $51^{\circ}03'$ and $51^{\circ}35'$ and between $36^{\circ}01'$ and $36^{\circ}05'$ latitude north. The area of the Karaj catchment inside Iran's territory is 824 km². The length of the longest branch of this river is 85 km. The average discharge volume of this river in the initial entrance of Karaj dam is 472 million cubic meters. The maximum current of this river occurs on May. This dam with optimal capacity of 195 million cubic meters is a multipurpose dam. Figure 1 shows the Karaj watershed location in IRAN.

Time series modelling. Time series is a collection of consecutive observations about a phenomenon, which occurs through time. Based on coherence or incoherence of observations, these time series are called continuous or discrete time series. The time series which is used in the present study is discrete time series. Because this time series is

calculated based upon a probability distribution, it is called a statistical time series. The time series model which is needed for prediction is called random stochastic models. The important types of random models, which have been used to describe time series is so called "static models". In these models, the process is assumed to balance around a stable mean level. But most of the time series, especially those which do not have a stable mean can be better shown as non-static models. A branch of non-static models are known as ARIMA collective average moving autoregressive models. These kinds of models provide chains of static and non-static models which can depict most of scientific time series almost perfectly.

FIGURE 1
The boundary of Karaj watershed

ARIMA term refers to a group of statistical models which have deterministic and probabilistic parameters of autoregressive AR and moving average MA seasonal and non-seasonal and, usually, are shown as follows: ARIMA (p, d, q) (P, D, Q) S which in this relation, P, p are the number of seasonal and non-seasonal parameters, respectively and Q, q are the number of MA seasonal and non-seasonal parameters, respectively. D and d are defined as the number of differences in seasonal level (like monthly) and non-seasonal level (like Annual). S is the number of seasons in a year.

Moving parameters depend directly on correlation with themselves in the various delays and correlated parameters depend directly on partial correlation. Time series are used for the production of synthetic data and forecast data on water resources. The simple form is AR (P). Autoregressive models are based on the random and correlated behavior of hydrologic data and are well known as Markov models. ARIMA models (p, q) are obtained by adding the moving average to the correlated models. Both of these models are mainly used for the production of different scenarios of synthetic time series and can be expected lower. Besides these models, time series methods ARIMA is used in its simple and seasonal form just for prediction of hydrological data on water resources. ARIMA model is shown in equation (1):

$$\Phi(B^w)\varphi(B)(1 - B^w)^D(1 - B)^d z_t = \Theta(B^w)\theta(B)\varepsilon_t + c \quad (1)$$

Where, ε_t is random variable; B is differencing operator, φ non-seasonal correlated parameter, θ non-seasonal moving parameter, Φ seasonal correlated parameter, Θ seasonal moving average parameter and c is unbiased parameter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Due to the necessity of normality in using time series, first these data were examined by drawing a normal graph. It is assumed that the classification of time series based on its statistical parameters would lead to a better normalized series in comparison to the usual transform methods such as natural logarithm. Therefore, we also assessed the monthly time series based on their statistical parameters and so, we categorized the time series into five seasons and also suppose that the whole series itself is a unique season which its return period is 12 months. Then for normalizing the data, the box-Cox and logarithmic transformation have been used. Therefore, we have to convert data to a normal distribution with an appropriate transformation method. One of the suitable conversion methods is Box-Cox (Equation 2).

$$\begin{cases} z = \frac{y^\lambda - 1}{\lambda g^{\lambda - 1}} & \lambda \neq 0 \\ z = g * \ln \lambda & \lambda = 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Where, "y" equals basic data, "z" is the variable, and "g" is geometric mean and a true quantity in the range of 3 to -3. In addition, the box plot of the time series in various months is drawn in order to classify data in different seasons and convert them to normal distribution due to the mentioned classification (Figure 2).

FIGURE 2
Plot of the series follows a normal distribution before transformation

According to the mentioned parameters, time series was classified into five seasons, the first

season consisted of December, January and February, the second season consisted of March, April and May, the third season consisted of June, July, the fourth season consisted of August, September and October and the fifth season consisted of November. The best parameter (λ) of the Box-Cox transformation method for each season was chosen by comparing the results with Kolmogrov-Smirnov test (Figure 3).

FIGURE 3
Kolmogrov-Smirnov goodness of fit plot of different seasons

FIGURE 4
Auto-correlation plot of the Elite model without deduction

Afterward, the results of study showed that the classification could not convert data to normal distribution properly and the results of abrupt

conversion and the conversion of classified data to each other are overlapped. Therefore, the conversion of unclassified data was used for the data under study with natural logarithm. After normalization of data by investigating the auto-correlation and partial auto-correlation figures, it revealed that the time series under study is not static (Figures 4 and 5).

FIGURE 5
Partial Auto-correlation plot of the Elite model without deduction

FIGURE 6
Auto-correlation plot of the Elite model with deduction

FIGURE 7
Partial Auto-correlation plot of the Elite model with deduction

Thus, simple seasonal deduction operations should be used to correct the instability. It is worth noting that the time series was maintained after simple operation of instability. But the time series

converted into a static status after the operation of seasonal deduction (Delayed 12 months). The reduction of autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation plots are also static status in the data and show the validity of the results (Figures 6 & 7).

Therefore, after the initial examination, to select the best model, 14 different scenarios were fitted to the values of data and Portmanteau (Equation 3) and Akaike tests (Equation 4) were operated on these models.

$$Q = (N - d) \sum_{k=1}^L r_k^2(\epsilon) \tag{3}$$

$$AIC(p, q) = N \ln(\sigma_\epsilon^2) + 2(p + q) \tag{4}$$

In the above equations, $rk(\epsilon)$ is the remaining auto-correlation, N is the number of data and 2 is error variance. It must be mentioned here that MINITAB 15 software was used to analyze different models. The results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1
The analyzed models for finding the best ARIMA model in terms of Akaike Criteria and SSE

Models	Akaike Criteria	SSE
ARIMA(1,1,1)(1,1,1) 12	2156	27.7
ARIMA(1,1,1)(0,0,0) 12	2724	66.5
ARIMA(1,1,1)(1,1,0) 12	2175	28.5
ARIMA(1,1,0)(1,1,1) 12	2279	33.6
ARIMA(0,1,1)(1,1,0) 12	2421	41.8
ARIMA(1,1,0)(0,1,1) 12	2277	33.5
ARIMA(1,1,0)(1,1,0) 12	2520	48.7
ARIMA(2,0,0)(0,1,1) 12	2154	27.6
ARIMA(2,0,0)(1,1,1) 12	2156	27.7
ARIMA(2,0,0)(2,1,1) 12	2152	27.5
ARIMA(1,0,0)(1,1,1) 12	2170	28.4
ARIMA(1,0,1)(2,1,1) 12	2135	26.8
ARIMA(1,0,0)(2,1,0) 12	2317	35.6
ARIMA(1,0,1)(1,1,1) 12	2137	26.9

Among the 55 years under study, 53 years were used to analyze models and 2 water years were used to verify the accuracy of model, in the end, the multiplying model ARIMA(1,0,1)(2,1,1)12 was chosen as the best model with regard to the tests. Figures of residual of auto-correlated and the partial auto-correlated (Figures 8 & 9) showed static state in data and proved the accuracy of results.

FIGURE 8
Auto-correlation residual plot of the Elite model

FIGURE 9
Partial Auto-correlation residual plot of the Elite model

The analysis have been done according to the best model via ARIMA (1, 0, 1) (2, 1, 1)12, with the best obtained parameters.

The parameter values are 0.84, 0, 0.57, -0.0158, -0.034, 1, 0.95 and 0.00008 respectively. Figures 10 and 11 show the verification process of modelling and also the correlation of calculating inflow obtained by the model and with the observed inflow for two years. Figures 12 and 13 shows the results for one year. As it is shown the elite model shows its good performance in predicting the inflow in coming months. It is also should mention that the performance of a model for 12 month lead time is better than for 24 months in terms of determination coefficient.

The results showed that the best model is ARIMA (1, 0, 1) (2, 1, 1)12 with the least squares mean square error. It should be mentioned that the obtained results of the survey indicate that the accuracy of the estimated values are lower than the true values and The predicted gap is more, the difference is more and the error rate increases. Therefore, these models cannot be used in the long term predictions and in case of using; these models

need to be updated. One of the disadvantages of these models, in case of the accuracy of the results, is once the new observation becomes available; Estimations of the model parameters cannot be modified or updated and analyzing is inevitable which completely fit the new models.

FIGURE 10

24 month forecast plot and comparing with the observed inflow

FIGURE 11

Plot of observed inflow versus forecasted inflow for 24 months

FIGURE 12

12 month forecast plot and comparing with the observed inflow

FIGURE 13

Plot of observed inflow versus forecasted inflow for 12 months

CONCLUSION

This paper investigates the results by comparing 5 seasonal and one non seasonal time series in the scale of yearly data in terms of preparing for normalization with Box- Cox and natural logarithm transformation and their impacts in the modeling and also forecasting in the mid- term periods. By using the transformation for achieving normal series, we assess the degree of normalization with the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test (K–S test). This test shows that although the seasonalization hypothesis at the first glance should be better than the natural logarithm, but the investigation has shown that the natural logarithm is better than the seasonalization. The methodology which used is time series modeling with the ARIMA type models. The ARIMA model is used to construct a purely statistical model for the observed data in order to forecast the future events based on the historical data. So on the basis of this approach, there has been used 14 different models with different logical parameters in order to choose the best model. The choice of the best model was implemented by considering the AKAIKE criterion that is suggested in many references in the field of time series modeling. The results of the modeling summarized above show that the ARIMA (1, 0, 1) (2, 1, 1)12 is the best model ($R^2= 0.78$) for forecasting the 12 months lead time and also the 24 months lead time ($R^2= 0.64$). So as the Coefficient of determination shows that we can accept the results with this approach and they can be considered as a good result in order to decide about your policies for managing water resources .

The choice of the most reasonable and robust technique should be made on the basis of the knowledge of the system, the input and output data, and the available modeling approaches. In general,

when there is a long term data series and there are no other data which shows the historical behavior of the considered basin for analyzing it more integrated, therefore, one of the best choices that are not time consuming and also reliable is time series modeling.

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